

COMPARISON OF SPORT TERMINOLOGIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Abdullayev Abdurashid Abdusattor O'g'li

O'qituvchi

Urinbekov Jasurbek

Co-Author

Fergana State University

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Annotation. This article analyzes the composition and definition of sport-related terminology, words, and phraseological units that function in modern linguistics. The research employs techniques such as analysis, definition, generalization, systematization, and numerical approaches. Terms form the foundation of sports terminology. The study differentiates the following forms of terminology: general sports units, simple units, and highly specialized units. Another outcome of our analysis of sports terminology is the grouping of selected units according to their source language.

Key words: sports terms, borrowing, anglicisms, affix word formation.

The article discusses the comparative typological analysis of Uzbek and English sports terminology in translation. It explores the conceptual content of the concept "sport" and its linguistic representation, emphasizing the classification and allocation of sports into groups based on distinctive features. The study also delves into the categorization of sports terms, distinguishing between terms related to the science of sports, sports terms, and industry-specific terms.

Furthermore, the article addresses the incorporation of borrowed words, particularly Anglicisms, into the Uzbek language, raising concerns among Uzbek linguists about language purity. The emergence of Anglicisms in Uzbek, influenced by English's status as the official language of the Olympic Committee and widespread use in sports media, prompts the need for their publication and linguistic analysis.

The authors provide examples of the translation and adaptation of English sports terms into Uzbek, aiming to maintain semantic accuracy while adhering to linguistic norms. They highlight the importance of preserving linguistic integrity by offering Uzbek equivalents for English terms and recommending against direct English pronunciation in certain cases.

Overall, the article's objective is to conduct a lexico-semantic study of selected sports terms borrowed from English into Uzbek, examining their

linguistic characteristics and word formation processes within the sports domain.

The study examines the borrowing of English sports terminology into the Uzbek language, drawing from Uzbek dictionaries. It notes that many sports terms in Uzbek originate from English due to the popularity of sports originating in the USA and the UK.

Examples of English sports terms adopted into Uzbek are provided across various sports, including tennis, golf, and surfing. These terms cover a wide range of activities and equipment used in each sport, such as different types of shots and strokes in tennis, club types and scoring in golf, and techniques and maneuvers in surfing.

The borrowing of English sports terms into Uzbek extends beyond nouns to include verbs and verbal nouns with the suffix "-er," indicating the performer of an action or the participant in an activity. For example, "coacher" refers to a sports coach, "jogger" to someone who runs, and "surfer" to someone who surfs. Additionally, compound words formed by combining two nouns are also observed, such as "boxer-short" for boxing shorts and "home-trainer" for an exercise device used at home.

Furthermore, the study identifies a group of sports terms in Uzbek formed by affixing "-er" to denote belonging to a profession or activity. These terms include "snowboarder," "rafter," and "basketball player," among others.

Finally, the study highlights the formation of compound words in Uzbek sports terminology using the root "board," as seen in terms like "skateboard," "snowboard," and "funboard," each referring to specific types of boards used in various sports activities.

The study identifies Uzbek words formed through hybridization, where two borrowed words from different languages are combined to create a new term. Examples include "autocross" and "autostart," combining "auto" from Greek and "cross" and "start" from English. Similarly, terms like "tennisman" and "rugbyman" are formed through the synthetic method of education, combining "tennis" or "rugby" with "man" instead of using the English expressions "tennis player" or "rugby player." Other examples include "recordman," "crossman," and "racingman," formed in the same manner.

The study emphasizes that the lexicon of a language is more susceptible to borrowing than its grammar, due to the frequent use and assimilation of new foreign words. The media plays a significant role in the dissemination and adoption of foreign terms, particularly in professions like journalism and sports

commentary, where immediate translation from a foreign language is often required.

Regarding sports vocabulary, the study notes that it is only partially professional, as physical culture and sports encompass activities beyond narrow professional interests. The media contribute to the enrichment of sports terminology with anglicisms such as "drop," "goal," "dribble," "penalty," "score," and "corner."

In conclusion, this article aims to raise awareness among language researchers about the evolving nature of our lexicon and the factors that contribute to its expansion. From advancements in technology to cultural and socio-political shifts, our vocabulary undergoes constant growth and transformation. As our lives change, so does our language, giving rise to new words and expressions. The analysis indicates a significant influence of the English language on relatively new sports terminologies in Uzbek, such as football, rugby, golf, tennis, and water polo. However, earlier forms of sports like wrestling, fencing, and billiards have fewer anglicisms in Uzbek terminology. Overall, the study reveals that the majority of borrowings in Uzbek sports terminology are anglicisms, which sometimes expand their meanings or acquire new semantics upon adoption into the language.

Navigating the meanings of newly coined terms can be challenging, but this paper provides a theoretical classification of common types of sport terms to assist learners in understanding their word formation. By categorizing words and phrases based on their origin, derivation, and etymology, this information facilitates comprehension and analysis of sport-related terminology. Furthermore, the proliferation of sportive neologisms underscores the dynamic nature of language and its role as a reflection of societal trends and developments. These terms have become ubiquitous across various domains of our society, highlighting language's capacity to adapt and evolve alongside human activities and interests. In essence, sport-related neologisms serve as compelling evidence that language is a living phenomenon, constantly responding to and shaping the world around us.

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